

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Modeling composition of properties of biogas produced from the Co-digestion of cow-dung and organic kitchen waste

Oji Akuma ^{1,*}, Nkemakolam Kelechi Daniel ¹, Ibifuro Altraide ² and Amodu Da-Silva ³

¹ Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria,

² World Bank African Center for excellence, Center for Oil field Chemical research. University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

³ Petroleum Training Institute, Effurun, Delta State, Nigeria.

GSC Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 13(01), 142–154

Publication history: Received on 08 September 2022; revised on 11 October 2022; accepted on 14 October 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscarr.2022.13.1.0278>

Abstract

Public concerns about climate change, air pollution, water quality and rising energy consumption have place pressure on producers and industry to reduce emissions and promote pollution-free sources of energy. One of the most generally available sources of renewable energy is biogas; hence, this study on kinetic modeling of the biogas composition was carried out at ambient condition for a period of 30 days to supplement energy requirements in farms and houses. The substrates, cow dung and organic kitchen waste were co-digested at different ratios for biogas production at laboratory scale. The digesters substrate had 3300g of feed each with varying ratios of 70:30 (Sample A), 50:50 (Sample B), 40:60 (Sample C), and 30:70 (Sample D) of cow dung to organic kitchen waste respectively. A biogas analyzer was used for the measurement of gas composition, biodigester operating parameter were measured using a multi-meter, while gas volume was obtained using calibrated floating drum. The model showed polynomial correlation as best fit using the R² method.

Keywords: Biogas; Biogas-analyzer; Co-Digestion; Cow-dung; Biodigesters; Correlation

1. Introduction

Nigeria is regarded as the giant of Africa because of her abundant potentials and the feat of having the largest population in Africa. As a country, Nigeria is endowed naturally with a lot of minerals such as coal, tin, columbite, iron ore, crude oil and gas, gold, lead, zinc, limestone. These minerals are natural substances which are obtained from the earth through mining. The harnessing of all the endowed natural resources for the generation of energy needed for both domestic and industrial use, and better utilization of all these minerals help to promote economic development such as creation of employment opportunities, aiding industrial development, promotion of economic and infrastructural development, help to improve the standard of living, earning of foreign exchange for Nigeria and so much more. The major sources of power in Nigeria are petroleum, water, Natural gas and Coal.

We can classify energy sources under two main parts which are the renewable and non-renewable sources of energy.

Renewable energy sources are those sources that are always naturally available in the environment, most times in excess, and can be replenished. They are "environment friendly" as they do not cause any natural imbalance. Renewable energy sources include Air (wind energy), water (hydro-electric energy), sun (solar energy), biomass (alternative fuels), hydrogen and inner earth layers (Geothermal energy).

* Corresponding author: Oji Akuma

Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Non renewable energy sources are those sources that are limited in their availability. Globally, the most preferred and large scale energy harvesting is through the nonrenewable sources, this is because it is easier to harvest on a large scale. Its sources are coal, natural gas, nuclear energy and petroleum.

It is believed in science that matter occupies space and space is limited, as a result, this phenomenon in turn will show that the fixed factor like space (environment) will be affected when a continuous factor like population growth is put on it. The space in this case is the geographical area of Nigeria, which is by nature limited to 923,768 sq km. The population was estimated to be about 120 million in 2005. [1]. Facts to know about Nigeria is that the current population of Nigeria is 193,409,540 as of Thursday, January 4, 2018, based on the latest United Nations estimates, the Nigerian population is equivalent to 2.53% of the total world population. Nigeria ranks number 7 in the list of countries by population. The population density in Nigeria is 210 per Km² (543 people per mi²).

Public concerns about climate change, air pollution, water quality and rising energy consumption all place pressure on producers and industry to reduce emissions and promote pollution-free sources of energy. One of the most generally available sources of renewable energy is biogas. Recently, several commercial large scale anaerobic digestion facilities have come upstream due to dwindling natural gas supplies in most of the developed countries. Small scale units are also being implemented to supplement energy requirements in farms and houses.

2. Literature survey

There are ten main sources of energy that are used to generate power in the world today. All of these different sources of energy are used primarily to produce electricity. Solar energy is a promising and freely available energy source for managing long term issues in energy crisis [2]. It involves conversion of energy directly from the sun into electricity either directly using a photovoltaic (PV) cell or indirectly using a solar power or a combination. According to [3] Wind energy is indigenous and can help reduce dependency on fossil fuels. Wind is caused by differential heating of the earth's surface by the sun. Hence it is an indirect form of solar energy and is always being replenished by the sun. Geothermal energy refers to the heat contained within the Earth that generates geological phenomena on a planetary scale [4]. The biggest disadvantage with geothermal energy is that it can only be produced at selected sites throughout the world. The Earth's geothermal resources are theoretically more than adequate to supply humanity's energy needs, but only a very small fraction may be profitably exploited. Hydrogen is a very efficient and clean fuel. Its combustion will produce no greenhouse gases, no ozone layer depleting chemicals, little or no acid rain ingredients and pollution [5]. Hydrogen is available with water and is the most common element available on earth. Water contains two-thirds of hydrogen and can be found in combination with other elements. Once it is separated, it can be used as a fuel for generating electricity. Hydrogen is a tremendous source of energy and can be used as a source of fuel to power ships, vehicles, homes, industries and rockets. It is completely renewable, can be produced on demand and does not leave any toxic emissions in the atmosphere. Tidal energy has the potential to play a valuable part in a sustainable energy future [6] Tides are produced which rush back and forth in the ocean. Tidal energy uses rise and fall of tides to convert kinetic energy of incoming and outgoing tides into electrical energy. Tidal energy is one of the renewable sources of energy and produce large energy even when the tides are at low speed. According to [7], Ocean waves are a huge, largely untapped energy resource, and the potential from extracting energy from waste is considerable. Wave energy is produced from the waves that are produced in the oceans. Wave energy is renewable, environment friendly and causes no harm to atmosphere. Producing wave energy can damage marine ecosystem and can also be a source of disturbance to private and commercial vessels. [8] defined hydroelectricity as the term referring to electricity generated by hydro-power; the production of electrical power through the use of the gravitational force of falling or flowing water. It is the most widely used form of renewable energy as it accounts for 16 percent of global electricity generation-3,427 terawatt-hours of electricity production in 2010. What many people are not aware of is that most of the developing cities and towns in the world rely on hydro-power, and have for the past century. Every time you see a major dam, it is providing hydro-power to an electrical station somewhere. The power of the water is used to turn generators to produce the electricity that is then used. The problem faced with hydropower right now is the ageing of the dams. Many of them need major restoration work to remain functional and safe, and that costs enormous sums of money.

Nuclear power and renewable energy are the main options to bring down the carbon intensity of commercial energy supply .Nuclear power falls short of the sustainability criteria and its public acceptance is low [9]. Nuclear power is actually one of the major renewable sources of energy available to the world. The energy is created through a specific nuclear reaction, which is then collected and used to power generators.

Traditionally fossil fuels have been used as the main resource to obtain energy but its use has several negative impacts such as global warming and air pollution [10].When most people talk about the different sources of energy they list natural gas, coal and oil as the options, these are all considered to be just one source of energy from fossil fuels. Fossil

fuels provide the power for most of the world, primarily using coal and oil. Oil is converted into many products, the most used of which is gasoline. The issue with fossil fuels is of two kinds. To get to the fossil fuel and convert it to use, there has to be a heavy destruction and pollution of the environment.

Biomass energy is produced from organic material and is commonly used throughout the world. Biomasses generally include crops, plants, trees, yard clippings, wood chips and animal wastes. Biomass energy is used for heating and cooking in homes and as a fuel in industrial production. This type of energy produces large amount of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere [11].

Many households in the world are facing the problem of inadequate supply of energy. The availability of other cooking fuel such as fuel wood, agricultural residues, dried dung and charcoal is also declining, while commercial fuel are mostly, too expensive. This simply means that the price of supplies of the fossil fuel will increase steadily. They will have great impact on developing countries that import energy. In this context, renewable energy source contributes to more secure energy supply. The renewable energy sources are better solution then fossil fuels [12].

The extensive depletion of non-renewable resources, particularly oil, along with a higher level of consumption will have a significant impact on the economic development of future generations. Development is limited by availability of natural resources and current development is approaching toward a near end due to nearby exhaustion of employed resources, because population is growing exponentially, whereas the resources and food supply is fixed [13] Pollution will further limit the availability of food. Another limiting factor is depletion of natural resources. As a result, raw material will become extremely expensive and the depletion of non-renewable resources will lead to sudden collapse of economic development.

Production of environment friendly energy from biogas, which is among the renewable energy sources, provides an environmentally less damaging way of obtaining energy by reducing CO₂ emission in environment. These renewable energy sources help in fighting against climate change and contribute to economic growth, job creation and increase in energy security. Even renewable energy technology has an impact on environment but their impact is much less than the impact of the fossil fuels and nuclear fuels. Global challenge of environment protection requires a modified and environment oriented energy system for the future, in order to slow down greenhouse gas emission. One of the ways must be massive effort to increase renewable energy sources such as biogas. [12].

According to [12] energy is the basis of human life, there is hardly any activity or moment that is independent of energy. Every moment of the day we are using energy. The early man used muscle power, then fire and animal power. Next, he learned to harness energy, convert it to useful form and put it to various uses. Energy sources are two types: they are conventional energy sources like coal, petroleum, natural gas etc. & non-conventional energy sources like solar cells, fuel cells, thermo-electric generator, thermal converter, solar power generation, wind power generation, geo-thermal energy generation, tidal power generation etc. Most of the energy consumption is from power generation, transportation, industry, and community sectors. Biogas, a clean and renewable form of energy, could very well be a substitute for conventional energy sources, such as fossil fuels (coal, crude oil, natural gas). Biogas comes as an efficient cost effecting method to generate power. Biogas production is clean, low carbon technology, useful for the efficient management and conservation of organic waste into clean renewable biogas and organic manure/fertilizer. Biogas obtained by anaerobic can be used as an energy source for various applications such as cooking, heating, space cooling and refrigeration, electricity generation and gaseous fuel for vehicle use. [14] In addition, biogas plant provides high quality organic manure with soil nutrient which in turn improve soil fertility.

Anaerobic digestion is a biological process that can convert organic substrates to biogas in the absence of oxygen. [15] One of the end products is biogas, which is used to create electricity and heat, or can be processed into renewable natural gas and fuels used in transportation., another end product is separated digested solids which can be applied directly to crop-land or converted into other products. Also, nutrients in the liquid stream are used in agriculture as bio-fertilizer.

The various interactions and reactions that take place among methanogens, non-methanogens and substrates fed into a digester are referred to as digestion. In the anaerobic digestion process, the organic matter is broken down by an association of microorganisms in the absence of oxygen and lead to the formation of digestate and biogas which mainly consist of methane and carbon dioxide. [16] Originally, anaerobic digestion was perceived as a two stage process involving the sequential action of acid forming and methane forming bacteria. Now, it is known to be a complex fermentation process brought about by the symbiotic association of different types of bacteria. [17][18][19] The products produced by one group of bacteria serve as the substrates for the next group.

The overall effects of this growth on the living standards, resources used and the environment will continue to change the Nigerian landscape for a very long period of time if nothing is done to checkmate the rapid population growth. These effects are presently felt most especially in energy consumption, carbon emissions, air pollution and human congestion.

Culture-independent methods for the identification and characterization of microbial communities involved in biogas production, have met considerable success in recent times [20][21]. Chouari et al.^[22], detected the constituents of more than 20 bacterial phyla from anaerobic (mostly methanogenic) waste and wastewater sludge. Using the culture-independent methods of them, Proteobacteria, Chloroflexi, Firmicutes and Bacteroidetes are most prominent. Besides that, in a separate study, characterization of anaerobic microbial community related to biogas production has revealed the presence of Firmicutes, Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria, Bacteroidetes, Acidobacteria, Spirochetes, [21]. Earlier studies have reported that the majority of the Archaeal community identified from anaerobic digesters are very similar to already identified methanogens such as *Methanosarcinabarkeri*, *Methanosarcinafriusis*, *Methanobacterium formicum*, while the remaining are related to thermophilic microbes such as *Crenarchaea* or *Thermoplasma* sp. [23].

These bacteria feed upon the initial feedstock, which undergoes a number of different processes converting it to intermediate molecules including sugars, hydrogen & acetic acid before finally being converted to biogas. Different species of bacteria are able to survive at different temperature ranges. Bacteria living optimally at temperatures between 35-40°C are called mesophiles or mesophilic bacteria. Some of the bacteria can survive at the hotter and more hostile conditions of 55-60°C, these are called thermophiles or thermophilic bacteria. Methanogens includes species that can grow in the hostile conditions of hydro-thermal vents. These species are more resistant to heat and can therefore operate at thermophilic temperatures, a property that is unique to bacterial families.

2.1. Biogas chemistry

The Chemistry of the different stages for the conversion of the substrate to biogas by the endogenous microorganism is shown in equations 1 to 6.

Biogas is a mixture of CO₂ and CH₄:

Methane is made of formate (HCOO⁻) or CO₂:

Methane is also made of acetate (CH₃COO⁻) that is, acetic acid:

Methane is made of alcohols like methanol:

3. Material and methods

With respect to the scope of this research work, the biodigester considered for the production of the biogas using cow dung and kitchen waste is the “floating drum digester”.

The following factors are considered for the selecting the floating drum in the production of biogas using cow dung and kitchen waste;

- The operation of the plant is easy to understand and operate.
- The gas drum is air tight
- The digester has a constant gas pressure as a result of the weight of the drum
- Increase in gas-volume is easily recognized by the position of the drum.
- The designing and fabricating of the floating drum digester is cost effective.

- It is durable depending on the nature of material used in fabrication.

A total of four biodigesters were used in the course of this experiment. Their component parts are listed below;

- Biodigester (20litres)
- Gas holder (18liters)
- Gas Outlet Pipe
- Valve

Biogas holder: This holds the substrates (cow dung and kitchen waste).

Biodigester: This is a smaller drum which is called “the gas holder drum”. It is a plastic bottle which is completely immersed into the paint bucket filled with the substrates in order to create an air-tight environment to create the anaerobic environment needed for biogas production.

Gas Outlet Pipe: This is a small pipe fitted on the top of the gas holder drum that allows the passage of gas to any external holding such as a burner for cooking or heating purposes.

Gas Valve: Regulates the flow of the biogas.

The gas holder drum was calibrated by making sure the valve is closed, water is poured in to fill the gas pipe after which the first 500ml of water from the measuring cylinder is poured into the gas holder drum and marked. This process is repeated until the gas holder is filled with water. The water is poured out of the gas holder drum and allowed to dry.

Four digesters were used for the experiment. The digesters held 3300g of feed each with varying ratios of 70:30 (Sample A), 50:50 (Sample B), 40:60 (Sample C), and 30:70 (Sample D) of cow dung to kitchen waste respectively. The dilution ratio was 1:3 of feed to water which follows Ojolo et al. [24] experiment.

A total of 9.9 litres was used to dilute the substrate in each paint bucket in order to achieve optimum slurry concentration. An agitator was used to agitate the mix. The slurry was covered with an inverted calibrated floating dome. A quick leak test was done. Gas valves were shut. The presence of water provides a favourable environment for microorganisms.

The pH, temperature and gas composition were measured every five (5) days using a multi-meter while the daily gas production volume was measured using the calibrated gas holder drum. This is achieved as the floating drum rises due to pressure in the paint bucket as gas produced increases. The value of gas produced is equal to the markings on the gas holder drum that coincident with the top of the paint bucket. Gas composition was also measured using a biogas analyzer. When the digester started producing gas, it was tested using a gas burner. Initially, it did not burn, but after some trials, it started burning producing a yellow flame and a clear blue flame later.

4. Results and discussion

The result of the gas produced by the different Cow-dung with Organic kitchen waste is presented in Table Fig. 1 to 4. The pH of sample A went from less acidic to more acidic (5.15 to 4.78) which agrees with Otun et al., [26] for sample B, C and D, the pH went from more acidic to less acidic which agrees with Dahunsi and Oranusi [27]. The pH variation most not be unconnected with the increasing concentration of CO₂ which is an acidic gas.

The temperature recorded an average of 26.65 °C for sample A. Samples B, C and D had average temperatures of 26.55 °C, 26.95 °C, and 26.42 °C respectively. All four samples' temperature were within same range hence, this experiment occurred under mesophilic temperature which agrees with Otun et al., [26]

Sample A, Table 1, had its highest methane content (100%LEL) on the 10th day after which it started reducing steadily. From Table 2, sample B had a methane content of 46%LEL on the 8th day and then 17%LEL on the 30th day. Sample C and sample D had similar behavior. Both increased steadily with their first peak hitting 58%LEL and 48%LEL on the 17th respectively after which they both reduced and went as high as 99%LEL on day 30. The methane content produced conforms with literature one of which is; for biogas to be flammable the methane content must be ≥ 40% [28].

Subsequently, Sample B was not graphed due to inadequate data which was as a result of no production on the stipulated days for checking gas composition. According to Sorathia et al., [29]; “If not stirred, the slurry will tend to settle out and form a hard scum on the surface, which will prevent release of biogas. This problem is much greater with vegetable waste than with manure, which will tend to remain in suspension and have better contact with the bacteria as a result.

Table 1 Biogas volume and composition for Sample A

Biodigester 1 (70:30) a								Gas composition					
Days	Vi (ml)	Vo (ml)	Vo-Vi	Burnt off	Cumulative	pH	Temp. (°C)	CH ₄	CO	O _{2i}	O _{2o}	CO ₂	H ₂ S
					Volume (ml)								
1	4000	4000	0	-	4000	7	-						
2	4000	5500	1500	-	5500	-	-						
3	5500	6500	1000	-	6500	-	-						
4	6500	6500	0	-	6500	-	-						
5	6500	8500	2000	1000	8500	5.15	27.2	58	2000	21	15	5.5	0
6	7500	9500	2000	-	10500	-	-						
7	9500	11000	1500		12000								
8	11000	13000	2000		14000								
9	13000	13500	500		14500								
10	13500	14000	500	7000	15000	5.25	27.5	100	2000	21	21		147
11	7000	8000	1000		16000								
12	8000	8000	0		16000								
13	8000	8000	0		16000								
14	8000	8000	0		16000								
15	8000	8000	0	1000	16000	5.02	27	38	2000	21	12	8.4	0
16	7000	7000	0		16000								
17	7000	7000	0		16000								
18	7000	7000	0		16000								
19	7000	7000	0		16000								
20	7000	8000	1000	2000	17000	4.72	25.2	22	2000	21	14	6.8	54
21	6000	6000	0		17000								
22	6000	6000	0		17000								
23	6000	9000	3000		20000								
24	9000	11000	2000		22000								
25	11000	11000	0	7000	22000	4.71	26	32	2000	21	17	3.8	47
26	4000	4000	0		22000								
27	4000	4000	0		22000								
28	4000	4000	0		22000								
29	4000	4000	0		22000								
30	4000	4000	0		22000	4.78	27	23	167	21	20	0.7	7

Table 2 Biogas volume and composition for Sample B

Bio digester 2 (50:50) b							Gas composition						
Days	Vi (ml)	Vo (ml)	Vo-Vi	Burnt off	Cumulative	pH	Temp. (°C)	CH ₄	CO	O _{2i}	O _{2o}	CO ₂	H ₂ S
					Volume(ml)								
1	2000	2000	0		2000							0	
2	2000	2000	0		2000								
3	2000	2000	0		2000								
4	2000	2000	0		2000								
5	2000	2000	0		2000								
6	2000	2000	0		2000								
7	2000	10000	8000		10000								
8	10000	10000	0	3500	10000	5.21	26.5	46	2000	21	19	1.9	27
9	6500	6500	0		10000								
10	6500	6500	0		10000								
11	6500	6500	0	4500	10000								
12	2000	2000	0		10000								
13	2000	2000	0		10000	5.15	26.4						
14	2000	2500	500		10500								
15	2500	2500	0		10500								
16	2500	2500	0		10500								
17	2500	2500	0	500	10500	4.9	26.9						
18	2000	2000	0		10500								
19	2000	2000	0		10500								
20	2000	2000	0		10500								
21	2000	2000	0		10500								
22	2000	2000	0		10500	5.1	26.8						
23	2000	3500	1500		12000								
24	3500	3500	0		12000								
25	3500	4500	1000		13000								
26	4500	4500	0		13000	5.53	26						
27	4500	5750	1250		14250								
28	5750	5750	0		14250								
29	5750	5750	0		14250								
30	5750	6500	750	4500	15000	5.69	26.7	17	2000	21	20	0.6	0

Table 3 Biogas volume and composition for Sample C

Biodigester 3 (40:60) c								Gas composition					
Days	Vi (ml)	Vo (ml)	Vo-Vi	Burnt off	Cumulative	pH	Temp. (°C)	CH ₄	CO	O _{2i}	O _{2o}	CO ₂	H ₂ S
					Volume (ml)								
1	1500	1500	0		1500							0	
2	1500	1500	0		1500								
3	1500	1500	0		1500								
4	1500	1500	0		1500								
5	1500	1500	0		1500								
6	1500	1500	0		1500								
7	1500	3000	1500		3000								
8	3000	9000	6000	500	9000	4.81	26.6	31	1982	21	19	1.8	11
9	8500	8500	0		9000								
10	8500	8500	0		9000								
11	8500	9000	500		9500								
12	9000	9000	0		9500								
13	9000	10750	1750	5750	11250	4.55	27.7	42	2000	21	17	4.1	6
14	5000	5000	0		11250								
15	5000	5500	500		11750								
16	5500	6000	500		12250								
17	6000	6500	500	1500	12750	4.65	28.6	58	1986	21	12	8.6	43
18	5000	5000	0		12750								
19	5000	5750	750		13500								
20	5750	6000	250		13750								
21	6000	6000	0		13750								
22	6000	6000	0	4000	13750	4.77	27.6	22	1777	21	18	2.4	18
23	2000	2500	500		14250								
24	2500	3000	500		14750								
25	2500	3000	500		15250								
26	3000	3000	0	500	15250	5.66	26.6	24	22	21	19	1.5	31
27	2500	5500	3000		18250								
28	5500	5500	0		18250								
29	5500	5500	0		18250								
30	5500	5500	0	3500	18250	5.66	24.6	99	1985	21	12	9.2	176

Table 4 Biogas volume and composition for Sample D

Biodigester 4 (30:70) d								Gas composition					
Days	Vi (ml)	Vo (ml)	Vo-Vi	Burnt off	Cumulative	pH	Temp. (°C)	CH ₄	CO	O _{2i}	O _{2o}	CO ₂	H ₂ S
					Volume (ml)								
1	1500	1500	0		1500							0	
2	1500	1500	0		1500								
3	1500	1500	0		1500								
4	1500	1500	0		1500								
5	1500	1500	0		1500								
6	1500	1500	0		1500								
7	1500	2000	500		2000								
8	2000	2000	0	500	2000	3.55	25.7	0	76	21	21	0	0
9	2000	2000	0		2000								
10	2000	2000	0		2000								
11	2000	9000	7000		9000								
12	9000	9000	0		9000								
13	9000	11000	2000	3000	11000	4.74	27.6	14	1990	21	17	3.8	3
14	8000	8000	0		11000								
15	8000	8000	0		11000								
16	8000	8000	0		11000								
17	8000	8500	500	7000	11500	4.91	27.1	48	2000	21	16	5.3	66
18	1500	1500	0		11500								
19	1500	2000	500		12000								
20	2000	3500	1500		13500								
21	3500	5500	2000		15500								
22	5000	5500	500	2000	16000	5.5	26.1	11	1568	21	20	1.1	19
23	3500	3500	0		16000								
24	3500	4000	500		16500								
25	4000	5000	1000		17500								
26	5000	5000	0	3500	17500	5.64	27.4	17	2000	21	8.5	12	18
27	1500	1500	0		17500								
28	1500	1500	0		17500								
29	1500	1500	0		17500								
30	1500	4500	3000	5000	20500	5.67	24.6	99	1975	21	12	9.2	39

Table 5 Cumulative Gas Volumes for All Samples

Day	Gas Volume			
	A	B	C	D
1	4000	2000	1500	1500
2	5500	2000	1500	1500
3	6500	2000	1500	1500
4	6500	2000	1500	1500
5	8500	2000	1500	1500
6	10500	2000	1500	1500
7	12000	10000	3000	2000
8	14000	10000	9000	2000
9	14500	10000	9000	2000
10	15000	10000	9000	2000
11	16000	10000	9500	9000
12	16000	10000	9500	9000
13	16000	10000	11250	11000
14	16000	10500	11250	11000
15	16000	10500	11750	11000
16	16000	10500	12250	11000
17	16000	10500	12750	11500
18	16000	10500	12750	11500
19	16000	10500	13500	12000
20	17000	10500	13750	13500
21	17000	10500	13750	15500
22	17000	10500	13750	16000
23	20000	12000	14250	16000
24	22000	12000	14750	16500
25	22000	13000	15250	17500
26	22000	13000	15250	17500
27	22000	14250	18250	17500
28	22000	14250	18250	17500
29	22000	14250	18250	17500
30	22000	15000	18250	20500

The CO content of sample A was 2000ppm until day 30 where it dropped to 167ppm, while, the CO content of sample C started higher than that sample D until day 13 through day 17 where both had the value. Both sample C and sample D experienced a drop in value from day 17 through day 22 with sample C still superseding sample D until a sudden

downward slope occurred with sample C which in turn made sample D higher. At day 30, both sample C and sample D had the same value.

The CO₂ content of sample A, sample C and sample D followed a undulating pattern having their highest peaks at 8.4%Vol on day 15, 8.6%Vol on day 17 and 12.3%Vol on day 26 respectively. Both sample C and sample D had 9.2%Vol on day 30 which agrees with Kavuma ^[30]

The O₂ content of sample A, sample C and sample D followed undefined pattern having their highest peaks at 20.8%Vol on day 10, 19%Vol on day 8 and 20.8%Vol on day 8 respectively. Both sample C and sample D had 11.6%Vol on day 30.

The H₂S content of sample A, sample C and sample D followed a zigzag pattern having their highest peaks at 147ppm on day 10, 176ppm on day 30 and 66ppm on day 17 respectively. Sample C and sample D didn't have same value on day 30. According to Suyog,^[31] the H₂S content should be between 20-20,000ppm

Cumulatively gas production Sample A (70:30) was more, as shown table 5. This is due to a higher amount of cow dung in Sample A. Sample D (30:70) was second highest. Sample B (50:50) had the least cumulative gas production with Sample C (40:60) as third highest.

4.1. Model of the Gas composition

Table 6 Biogas composition correlation for Sample A

	Linear Correlation	Polynomial
Time Vs CH ₄	$y = -2.5403x + 94.612$ $R^2 = 0.495$	$y = -0.0113x^4 + 0.908x^3 - 25.69x^2 + 296.65x - 1089$ $R^2 = 0.9789$
Time Vs CO ₂	$y = -0.2161x + 9.4911$ $R^2 = 0.3887$	$y = 0.0002x^4 - 0.0119x^3 + 0.2662x^2 - 1.9556x + 9.5198$ $R^2 = 1$
Time Vs CO	$y = -57.619x + 2808.5$ $R^2 = 0.4024$	$y = -0.1192x^4 + 8.0703x^3 - 194.45x^2 + 1958.2x - 4871.6$ $R^2 = 0.9921$
Time Vs H ₂ S	$y = -1.1758x + 65.233$ $R^2 = 0.0294$	$y = -0.0278x^4 + 2.1811x^3 - 60.753x^2 + 701.66x - 2724.6$ $R^2 = 0.7481$

Table 7 Biogas composition correlation for Sample C

	Linear Correlation	Polynomial
Time Vs CH ₄	$y = 1.5383x + 16.259$ $R^2 = 0.1888$	$y = 0.0065x^4 - 0.4326x^3 + 9.8726x^2 - 90.559x + 317.85$ $R^2 = 0.9756$
Time Vs CO ₂	$y = 0.1417x + 1.8595$ $R^2 = 0.1142$	$y = 0.0011x^4 - 0.078x^3 + 1.8503x^2 - 17.479x + 58.4$ $R^2 = 0.9148$
Time Vs CO	$y = -40.387x + 2406.1$ $R^2 = 0.1774$	$y = 0.3321x^4 - 23.927x^3 + 602.45x^2 - 6254.2x + 24380$ $R^2 = 0.8812$
Time Vs H ₂ S	$y = 5.5079x - 58.985$ $R^2 = 0.4966$	$y = 0.0131x^4 - 0.9144x^3 + 22.68x^2 - 232.34x + 832.29$ $R^2 = 0.9947$

Table 8 Biogas composition correlation for Sample D

	Linear Correlation	Polynomial
Time Vs CH ₄	$y = 2.9411x - 25.361$ $R^2 = 0.4344$	$y = 0.0086x^4 - 0.5933x^3 + 14.145x^2 - 135.47x + 446.05$ $R^2 = 0.9632$
Time Vs CO ₂	$y = 0.4321x - 3.071$ $R^2 = 0.5648$	$y = -0.0015x^4 + 0.1123x^3 - 3.0531x^2 + 34.532x - 132.64$ $R^2 = 0.7645$
Time Vs CO	$y = 60.265x + 436.37$ $R^2 = 0.4197$	$y = 1.1613x^3 - 73.729x^2 + 1491.9x - 7678.5$ $R^2 = 0.9248$
Time Vs H ₂ S	$y = 1.2191x + 0.5982$ $R^2 = 0.1644$	$y = 0.0098x^4 - 0.7195x^3 + 18.403x^2 - 188.97x + 660.83$ $R^2 = 0.7013$

The correlation on the biogas constituents including, CH₄, CO₂, CO and H₂S for the three samples A, C and D is presented in table 6, 7 and 8. All the models generated by the kinetics of the samples showed poor linear correlation, while the polynomial correlation of the 4th order had the best fit for the different ratios.

Sample B had a staggered correlation and was not presented.

5. Conclusion

The results obtained from the experiment carried out using cow dung and organic kitchen waste has been presented. In this study four (4) sample, labeled A, B, C, and D of different substrate ratio was experimented to understand the behavior of the various ratio based on the constitutes of the biogas produced. The kinetic model showed polynomial correlation as the best fit for all the samples. This project acts as sensitization to researchers on the efficient utilization of cow dung and organic kitchen waste using a low-cost bio digester which has low cost of construction, and maintenance ease to produce biogas for heat and electricity in farms and households. The results show that there is variation in the constituent biogas and the model that best fit in describing the different ratios.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

We wish to acknowledge the assistance of the Center for Gas, Refining and Petrochemical Engineering, University of Port Harcourt and also the World Bank African Center for excellence, Center for Oil field Chemical research. University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Thank you for the research support.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

We wish to state that there is no conflict of interest and that this is the original work of the authors.

References

- [1] Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR,2007), Nigeria. <http://www.DPR.gov.ng>
- [2] Kannan, N., & Vakeesan, D. "Solar energy for future world: A review" *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 2016, pg. no: 1092-1105.
- [3] Herbert G, Iniyani S., Sreevalsan E., Rajapandian S. "A review of wind energy technologies. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. "2007, pg. no: 6
- [4] Dickson, M. H., & Fanelli, M.. "Geothermal energy: Utilization and Technology" Routledge, 2013.
- [5] Veziroglu T. "21st Century's Energy: Hydrogen Energy System" 2007.
- [6] Rourke, F. O., Boyle, F., & Reynolds, A.. "Tidal energy update 2009" *Applied Energy*, 2010 pg no: 398-409.

- [7] Drew, B., Plummer, A. R., & Sahinkaya, M. N. "A review of wave energy converter technology" Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part A: Journal of Power and Energy, 2009, pg no. 887-902.
- [8] Bagher, A. M., Vahid, M., Mohsen, M., & Parvin, D. "Hydroelectric energy advantages and disadvantages." American Journal of Energy Science, 2015, pg no: 17-20.
- [9] Verbruggen, A. "Renewable and nuclear power: A common future?" Energy Policy, 2008. Pg no: 4036-4047.
- [10] Martins, F., Felgueiras, C., & Smitková, M. "Fossil fuel energy consumption in European countries" Energy Procedia, 2018, pg no: 107-111.
- [11] Rinkesh, K. Conserve Energy Future, 2009
- [12] Khalil, A., & Asheibe, A. "The chances and challenges for renewable energy in Libya." Proceedings of the Renewable Energy Conference, 2015. Pg no:1-6.
- [13] Panayotou, T., "An Inquiry into Population, Resources and Environment in the Impact of Population Growth on Well-being in Developing Countries" Springer Verlag, New York, 1996 pg no: 219-258.
- [14] Obrecht, M, Denac, M. "Biogas - a sustainable energy source: new measures and possibilities for Slovenia". Journal of Energy Technology, 2011, pg no: 11-24.
- [15] Zhang, Q., Hu, J., & Lee, D. J. " Biogas from anaerobic digestion processes: Research updates" Renewable Energy, 2016, pg no: 108-119
- [16] Al Seadi, T. Biogas handbook, 2008
- [17] Edmond-Jacques, N. " Biomethanation process. Biotechnology" Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN): Renewable Energy Master Plan. 8, 1986, pg no: 207-267.
- [18] Speece, R. E. "Anaerobic biotechnology" Environ Sci Technol, 1983 pg no: 417A.
- [19] . Kosaric, N., & Blaszczyk, R. "Industrial effluent processing." Encyclopedia of microbiology, 1992, pg no: 473-491
- [20] Wirth, R., Kovács, E., Maróti, G., Bagi, Z., Rákhely, G., & Kovács, K. L.. "Characterization of a biogas-producing microbial community by short-read next generation DNA sequencing." Biotechnology for biofuels, 2012, pg no: 1-16.
- [21] Chojnacka, A., Szczęsny, P., Błaszczyk, M. K., Zielenkiewicz, U., Detman, A., Salamon, A., & Sikora, A. "Noteworthy facts about a methane-producing microbial community processing acidic effluent from sugar beet molasses fermentation" PLoS One, 2015.
- [22] Chouari, R., Le Paslier, D., Daegelen, P., Ginestet, P., Weissenbach, J., & Sghir, A. "Novel predominant archaeal and bacterial groups revealed by molecular analysis of an anaerobic sludge digester" Environmental microbiology, 2005, pg no: 1104-1115.
- [23] Godon, J. J., Zumstein, E., Dabert, P., Habouzit, F., & Moletta, R.. "Molecular microbial diversity of an anaerobic digester as determined by small-subunit rDNA sequence analysis." Applied and environmental microbiology, 1997, pg no: 2802-2813.
- [24] Ojolo, S., Oke, S., Animasahun, K., & Adesuyi, B. (2007). Utilization of Poultry, Cow and Kitchen Wastes for Biogas Production: A Comparative Analysis. Iran. J. Environ. Health. Sci. Eng., Vol. 4, No. 4, pp. 223-228.
- [25] Khandelwal K. and Dr. Vibha K. Gupta. "Popular Summary of the Test Reports on Biogas Stoves and Lamps prepared by testing institutes in China, India and the Netherlands" 2009.
- [26] Otun, T., Ojo, O., Ajibade, F., & Babatola, J. O. "Evaluation Of Biogas Production From The Digestion And Codigestion Of Animal Waste, Food Waste And Fruit Waste." International Journal of Energy and Environmental Research, 2016, pp.8.
- [27] Dahunsi, S. O., & Oranusi, U. S. "Co-digestion of Food Waste and Human Excreta for Biogas Production" British Biotechnology Journal, 2013, pg no: 485-499.
- [28] Monnet, F. "An Introduction to Anaerobic Digestion of Organic Wastes" 2003.
- [29] Sorathia, H. S., Rathod, D. P., & Sorathiya, A. S. "Bio-gas generation and factors affecting the bio-gas generation – a review study." International Journal of Advanced Engineering Technology (IJAET), 2012.
- [30] Kavuma, C. "Variation of Methane and Carbon dioxide. Sweden" 2013
- [31] Suyog, V. "Biogas production from kitchen waste." Rourkela: National Institute of Technology, 2011.